

BCAA Supplementation in Mice with Diet-Induced Obesity Alters the Metabolome Without Impairing Glucose Homeostasis

Supplemental Figures

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D Insulin Tolerance Tests

Figure S1. BCAA supplementation does not affect caloric intake, glucose tolerance or insulin sensitivity in female HFHS-fed mice. **A)** Cumulative caloric food intake, **B)** cumulative caloric water intake, and **C)** cumulative caloric food and water intake from wild-type female mice fed chow or HFHS diet with or without BCAA supplementation in water. **D)** Insulin tolerance tests performed in mice following a 5-hour food removal at different weeks of diet and treatment with BCAAs in water. Insulin dose 0.5U/kg BW. Chow n=11, HFHS n=11, HFHS+BCAA n=12. *p<0.05 HFHS and HFHS+BCAA vs chow. #p<0.05 HFHS+BCAA vs HFHS and chow.

High Fat High Sucrose Diet – Liver

Acylcarnitines

Acyl CoAs

Figure S2A. HFHS feeding, and not BCAA supplementation, drives most changes in the liver metabolome in female HFHS-fed mice.

Figure S2A. *HFHS feeding, and not BCAA supplementation, drives most changes in the tissue metabolome in female HFHS-fed mice.* Heat map for all measured acylcarnitines and acyl CoAs in **A)** liver, **B)** gastrocnemius, and **C)** PG WAT from chow and HFHS-fed mice supplemented with or without BCAAs in water. Mice were fasted overnight and tissues collected following a 6-hour refeeding period. n=6/group.

High Fat High Sucrose Diet – Gastrocnemius

Figure S2B. HFHS feeding, and not BCAA supplementation, drives most changes in the gastrocnemius metabolome in female HFHS-fed mice.

High Fat High Sucrose - PG WAT

Acylcarnitines

Acyl CoAs

Figure S2C. HFHS feeding, and not BCAA supplementation, drives most changes in the PG WAT metabolome in female HFHS-fed mice.

Figure S3. Effect of BCAA supplementation on BCAA-derived C3 and C5 acylcarnitine levels in liver, gastrocnemius, and PG WAT from wild-type female mice on HFHS diet supplemented with or without BCAAs in water. Mice were fasted overnight and tissues collected following 6 hours of refeeding. n=6/group. *p<0.05 HFHS or HFHS+BCAA vs. chow.

Figure S4. Minimal effect of HFHS diet and BCAA treatment on amino acid levels in metabolic tissues from chow and HFHS-fed female mice. Amino acid levels from **A**) liver, **B**) gastrocnemius, and **C**) PG WAT from chow and HFHS-fed wild-type female mice supplemented with or without BCAAs in water (same mice as in Figures 1-3). Mice were fasted overnight and tissues were collected following a 6-hour refeeding period. $n=6/\text{group}$. * $p<0.05$ HFHS or HFHS+BCAA vs. chow, # $p<0.05$ HFHS+BCAA vs. HFHS.

Figure S5. BCAA supplementation does not worsen insulin resistance in wild-type female mice fed a HFD. **A**) Body weight, **B**) fat and lean mass, **C**) insulin tolerance test 5 hours after food removal, and **D**) valine oxidation from tissue explants (BAT, PG WAT, SQ WAT, EDL and soleus) from wild-type female mice fed a chow or HFD with or without BCAA supplementation in water. n=6-7/group for *in vivo* studies, n=4-7 for *ex vivo* oxidation studies. *p<0.05 HFD or HFD+BCAA vs. chow, #p<0.05 HFD+BCAA vs. HFD.

A

High Fat Diet – ALL SERUM ACYLCARNITINES

Figure S6A. *HFD feeding, and not BCAA supplementation, drives most changes in the serum and tissue metabolomes from male HFD-fed mice.* Heat map for all measured acylcarnitines and acyl CoA levels in **A)** serum, **B)** liver, **C)** gastrocnemius, and **D)** PG WAT from chow and HFD-fed male mice supplemented with or without BCAAs in water (same mice as in Figure 5). Mice were fasted overnight and tissues collected following a 6-hour refeeding period.

High Fat Diet - Liver

Figure S6B continued. *HFD feeding, and not BCAA supplementation, drives most changes in the liver metabolome from male HFD-fed mice.*

High Fat Diet – Gastrocnemius

Acylcarnitines

Acyl CoAs

Figure S6C continued. *HFD* feeding, and not *BCAA* supplementation, drives most changes in the gastrocnemius metabolome from male *HFD*-fed mice.

High Fat Diet - PG WAT

Acylcarnitines

Acyl CoAs

Figure S6D continued. *HFD feeding, and not BCAA supplementation, drives most changes in the PG WAT metabolome from male HFD-fed mice.*

Figure S7. Effect of BCAA supplementation on BCAA-derived C3 and C5 acylcarnitine levels in liver, gastrocnemius, and PG WAT from wild-type male mice on HFD diet supplemented with or without BCAAs in water. Mice were fasted overnight and tissue collected following 6 hours of refeeding. n=6/group. *p<0.05 HFD or HFD+BCAAs vs chow.

A**High Fat Diet - SERUM**

Figure S8. Minimal effect of BCAA supplementation on amino acid levels in serum and metabolic tissues from chow and HFD-fed male mice. Amino acid levels from **A**) serum, **B**) liver, **C**) gastrocnemius, and **D**) PG WAT from chow and HFD-fed wild-type male mice supplemented with or without BCAAs in water. Mice were fasted overnight and tissues were collected following a 6-hour refeeding period (same mice as in Figures 5-7). Chow n=4, HFD and HFD+BCAA n=6/group. *p < 0.05 vs chow, #p < 0.05 vs HFD.

D

High Fat Diet - PG WAT

Figure S8 continued. Minimal effect of BCAA supplementation on amino acid levels in serum and metabolic tissues from chow and HFD-fed male mice.

Supplemental Table 1. *Composition of high fat-high sucrose (HFHS) and high fat (HFD) diets used in this study.* Composition is presented as % of kcal with individual source nutritional components listed below.

High fat-high sucrose diet (HFHS; Research Diets D12079Bi)		High fat diet (HFD; Harlan Teklad TD.93075)	
Caloric Information	% kcal	Caloric Information	% kcal
Protein	17	Protein	21.2
Carbohydrate	43	Carbohydrate	24
Fat	40	Fat	54.8
Energy Density	4.67 kcal/g	Energy Density	4.8 kcal/g
Ingredient	g/1001.54g	Ingredient	g/kg
Casein, Lactic, 30 Mesh	195	casein	289
Methionine, DL	3	DL-Methionine	3.33
Sucrose, fine granulated	350	Sucrose	90.5
Corn Starch	50	Corn Starch	207.3
Corn Oil	10	Corn Oil	16
Butter, anhydrous	200	Hydrogenated Veg Oil	274.1
S10001A (mineral)	17.5	Mineral Mix, AIN-76 (170915)	46.66
Calcium Carbonate, light, USP	4	Calcium Carbonate	6.66
Lodex 10	100	Cellulose	53.12
Solka Floc, FCC200	50	Vitamin Mix, Teklad (40060)	13.33
Calcium Phosphate, dibasic	17.5		
Choline Bitartrate	2		
V10001C (vitamin)	1		
Ethoxyquin (anti-oxidents)	0.04		
Cholesterol	1.5		

Supplemental Table 2. Summary of components of the BCAA-related metabolic signature in HFHS-fed female mice and HFD-fed male mice. NM indicates not measured.

	HFHS (vs chow)	HFHS+BCAA (vs HFHS)	HFD (vs chow)	HFD+BCAA (vs HFD)
Ad-lib fed state				
BCAAs (plasma)	↔	↑	NM	NM
BCKAs (plasma)	↔ (KIC, KIV), ↑ KMV	↑ (all)	NM	NM
6-hour refed state				
BCAAs (serum)	NM	NM	↔	↑ (VAL)
BCKAs (serum)	NM	NM	↔	↑ (all)
BCAAs (liver, PG WAT and muscle tissues)	↓ all, Liver ↔ all, PG WAT ↔ ILE or VAL, Quad ↑ LEU, Quad	↑ all, Liver ↔ all, PG WAT ↔ all, Quad	↓ VAL Liver ↔ LEU/ILE Liver ↔ all, PG WAT, Gastroc	↑ VAL Liver ↔ LEU/ILE Liver ↑ all, Gastroc ↔ all, PG WAT
BCKAs (liver, PG WAT and muscle tissues)	↔	↔	↔	↔
C3/C5 ACs (serum)	NM	NM	↓	↑
C3/C5 ACs (liver)	↔↔↔	↔↔↔	↓↔↔	↔↔↔
C3/C5 ACs (PG WAT)	↓↓	↔↔↔	↓↓	↔↔↔
C3/C5 ACs (gastroc)	↔↔↑	↔↔↔	↔↔↔	↔↔↔
C5-OH/C3-DC AC (serum)	NM	NM	↔	↑
C5-OH/C3-DC AC (liver)	↔	↑	↓	↔
C5-OH/C3-DC AC (PG WAT)	↔	↔	↔	↔
C5-OH/C3-DC AC (gastroc)	↔	↑	↓	↑
Ex vivo				
Valine Oxidation: WAT	NM	NM	↓	↔
Valine Oxidation: Muscle	NM	NM	↔	↑
Leucine Oxidation: WAT	NM	NM	↓	↔
Leucine Oxidation: Muscle	NM	NM	↔	↔